

Aesthetic Education in the Uzbek Family as the Basis for the Formation of a Harmonious Personality

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Abstract. *The article examines the role of the family as the most important social institution in raising children based on Uzbek national traditions. It emphasizes the importance of a harmonious combination of aesthetic, spiritual and cultural values in the development of a child's personality. Key aspects of education are analyzed, including instilling aesthetic taste, respect for art and nature, as well as the use of cultural heritage to form moral ideals. Particular attention is paid to the role of grandparents, as well as the importance of public policy in strengthening family values. A conclusion is made about the importance of aesthetic education as the basis for the formation of future citizens capable of combining national traditions with the challenges of modern society.*

Key words: *Uzbek family, aesthetic education, national values, harmonious development, culture, traditions, spiritual ideals, raising children.*

Introduction

The family has always occupied a central place in the socio-cultural life of our society. It is considered not only as a fundamental institution that ensures the continuation of the family line, but also as a key factor in the formation of a

harmonious and sustainable society. In the context of modern state policy, issues of strengthening family values and raising children are particularly relevant, which is expressed in priority national programs, such as the concept of "Healthy mother, healthy child, healthy society". This program, aimed at creating a healthy social environment, is already bringing tangible results, confirmed by statistical data on the growth in the number of families and the sustainable strengthening of their role in society.

Historically, in Uzbek society, the family was the core around which cultural and moral guidelines were formed. Great thinkers such as Alisher Navoi emphasized the importance of social associations such as mahallas, which contribute to the harmonious development of society. Today, the mahalla remains an important support in solving socio-economic and educational problems, which is especially important in the context of raising children, reflecting national and mental values.

Raising the younger generation in the spirit of aesthetic culture, morality and harmony between traditions and modernity is one of the key tasks of the modern Uzbek family. A unique synthesis of national traditions and current demands of the time allows us to preserve a rich cultural heritage, while developing children's ability to adapt to the challenges of the modern world.

The purpose of this article is to analyze the role of the family as a social institution, its importance in raising children and forming a national mentality. Particular attention is paid to the study of the aesthetic and cultural aspects of education, which play a decisive role in creating a harmonious and sustainable society.

I. LITERATURE REVIEW

In our society, the family is considered a sacred value, since it is the basis for the development of the country. The media emphasizes that the family and the neighborhood environment play an important role in raising children. It is especially worth noting that in our country, family and child rearing issues have become a priority of state policy. The implementation of the concept of "Healthy mother, healthy child, healthy society" continues to yield tangible results. According to statistics, over ten thousand new families are created in the country every year, and their total number already exceeds 8.2 million.

Family and neighborhood occupy a special place in our mentality, since the family is the main social institution responsible for the continuation of the family line, the birth and upbringing of children. Raising children in the family is becoming an increasingly important task that requires awareness and responsibility. Today, many studies are being conducted on family issues, the birth and upbringing of children, as well as the practical aspects of creating a favorable environment.

The main goal of these studies is to raise children who correspond to our cultural and mental values, as well as to create a healthy atmosphere in our neighborhoods. In this regard, the coordinated activities of assistants to district and city khokims, youth leaders, women's activists of mahallas, and law enforcement officers play an important role. These efforts are aimed at developing entrepreneurship, reducing unemployment and poverty, which is carried out in close cooperation with mahalla chairmen.

The term "mahalla" has deep historical roots and is mentioned in the works of great thinkers of the past. For example, Alisher Navoi used the word "Mahallot" to describe the association of people who have adapted to territorial conditions. This indicates that the mahalla as a form of social association existed in ancient times and is the basis of modern civil society.

Sh.M. Mirziyoyev notes the important wisdom: "... education begins with the family. In this context, the family is considered as the foundation where the principles of a healthy and harmonious society are laid. The stronger and more mature the family, the more stable and proportionate the society develops" [1;72-73]. Since ancient times, Uzbek families have been famous for their large families and commitment to traditional values. In modern conditions, national traditions play a key role in raising children, successfully combining with the demands of the time. Such a synthesis allows us to preserve unique cultural characteristics, while shaping children who are ready for the challenges of the modern world.

Raising children in an Uzbek family in the national spirit, developing their aesthetic perception and forming refined feelings are one of the main tasks. The family, as the fundamental unit of society, plays a key role in shaping its structure.

II. METHODOLOGY & EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

The family has a complex and multifaceted structure, including various aspects: natural and biological (childbearing, sexual relations), economic (property ties, housekeeping) and spiritual (feeling of affection between spouses, parents and children). It is the harmonious combination of these elements that creates the basis for raising children in the national spirit, strengthening family values and developing society as a whole [2;241]. In the aesthetic education of a child in the family, observation, perception of the beauty of reality and the cultivation of aesthetic taste, ideal are of great importance. They should also be educated, instilling in them a passion for the beauty and art of nature.

Raising a child in an Uzbek family requires taking into account his individual interests and inclinations. However, in some cases, parents can impose their preferences on their children, ignoring their personal interests. In addition, the employment of parents can cause insufficient attention to the formation of the child's personality.

Nevertheless, Uzbek families are famous for raising young people with a creative approach and aesthetic thinking, which is manifested in the desire for art, new ideas and ideological development. Education in this vein is based on a harmonious combination of religious and secular values, reflected in different aspects of life: words, music, color images and patterns. The main principles of this approach include:

1. The desire for rationality, which is expressed through words.
2. Formation of an ordered system of life, ensuring harmony.
3. Delicacy, as the foundation of the culture of relationships.
4. Classification of reality, contributing to understanding the world around us.
5. The principle of obedience, which develops respect for elders and discipline.

These principles form the basis for harmonious relationships in the family, strengthening it and creating conditions for raising a healthy, socially adapted child. In addition, harmony in art, for example, in music, where the melody becomes a reflection of the orderliness of the way of life, occupies a significant place in the aesthetic education of the child.

Following such principles not only helps to create strong family ties, but also helps to form worthy citizens of society from children. However, the most important role in this is played by the example of parents and adults, who through their behavior lay the foundation of moral and aesthetic values in the younger generation.

Aesthetic thinking in the Uzbek family originates from the rich spiritual heritage of ancestors, which is passed down from generation to generation through traditions filled with deep meaning. These family traditions serve as the basis for education, where art becomes an important tool for shaping the worldview and aesthetic taste of children.

Ornaments, for example, like patterns in the art of calligraphy, are not just visible beauty, but symbols that can awaken spiritual experiences and form aesthetic perception. These images, imbued with a deep oriental style, affect the heart and mind, forming exquisite aesthetic thinking in young people. The Uzbek family, continuing its centuries-old traditions, strives to preserve and develop these cultural values, connecting the past with the present for the sake of shaping the future.

III. RESULTS

Particular attention is paid to raising children in the spirit of aesthetic culture. The high level of interest of older family members in literature, music and other types of art influences the child's perception of such concepts as beauty, goodness and truth. From an early age, the child begins to understand the difference between good and bad, beautiful and ugly.

At the same time, it is important to take into account the individual interests of the child. If a parent notices that the child has a penchant for a certain type of art, sport or other activity, it is important to support this interest. Developing aesthetic taste and cultural perception from a young age helps to form a harmonious, creative and socially responsible personality.

Raising a child in an Uzbek family has always been based on love, respect and support for his interests. Parents strive to create an atmosphere of goodwill, free communication and harmony for their children in order to develop their aesthetic feelings and love for the beauty of the world around them.

Particular attention is paid to developing a child's fine taste and the ability to notice the beauty in nature, art and life. In the process of education, children learn to appreciate the beauty of reality, develop their intellect, aesthetic sense and interest in artistic culture. Parents try to instill in their children a sense of beauty and the ability to distinguish beauty from ugliness, and also cultivate in them such qualities as hard work, joy, warmth and kindness.

These spiritual values are reflected even in folk wisdom, where the beauty of a person is emphasized not by external features, but by the richness of the soul and moral perfection. Through such upbringing, parents pass on to their children the best traditions of their ancestors, educate them in the spirit of spiritual maturity, respect for art and the pursuit of excellence. Another important aspect of aesthetic education in the Uzbek family is the strictness of the father and the kindness of the mother. Because the father from a young age encourages his child to show love for work, enjoy the beauty of reality, show high aesthetic talent in behavior, art and stay away from disgusting and ugly, tasteless events. “The role and significance of historical memory, the collective virtue of the people, sympathy and feeling of the Motherland, hard work, humanism, etc. in the formation and development of the national mentality of youth serve as factors of a great educational example” [3;146]. The upbringing of children in an Uzbek family is aimed at developing high human feelings, striving for internal and external perfection, as well as mental acuity. Mothers play a special role in this, making sure that their children grow up in an atmosphere of harmony, listen to pleasant music, enjoy the beauty of nature and enjoy life. Such impressions contribute to the development of subtle aesthetic feelings and the ability to appreciate beauty in a child.

The contribution of grandparents, who pass on not only love but also life wisdom to their grandchildren, is invaluable. Telling fairy tales, stories and legends, they awaken courage, bravery, purity and nobility in children. Particular attention is paid to describing the beauty of nature and the harmony of the surrounding world, which helps children develop subtle perception, form aesthetic ideals and a rich inner world.

Thus, the legacy of aesthetic education, passed down from generation to generation, continues to be an important component of the formation of the younger generation. The use of cultural values of the Uzbek people, masterpieces of art and achievements of science in education contributes to the harmonious development of the individual.

An axiological approach to the study of emotional experiences of young people opens up creative prospects. The more philosophical methods are used in education, the more deeply spiritual and moral ideals are understood. The aesthetic heritage of the Uzbek family, built on original principles and centuries-old traditions, becomes the basis for the formation of a holistic worldview, which is of particular importance for the development of future generations.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the family in Uzbek society has always remained the basis of stability and development, forming cultural and spiritual values that are passed on from generation to generation. Raising children based on respect, love and understanding continues to be a priority task that requires attention not only from parents, but also from the whole society. An important aspect of this process is the synthesis of traditional values with modern requirements, which allows us to form a harmonious personality ready for the challenges of the modern world. Education in the spirit of aesthetics, love for art, nature and life in general develops in children subtle feelings and the ability to appreciate the beauty of the world around them, which contributes to their spiritual and moral growth.

The importance of the role of the family in education becomes even more obvious in the context of the development of national consciousness and the strengthening of social ties, where the key aspects are love for the Motherland, hard work and mutual support. Harmony in the family, which combines strict principles and kindness, as well as attention to cultural heritage, is the key to the formation of a generation capable of contributing to the development of society. Ultimately, traditions based on high moral values continue to serve as the foundation for the formation of future generations, educating them in the spirit of respect, love and the pursuit of excellence.

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